

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Solutions ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) each of DOPA (B.D.H.) with addition of concentrated H_2SO_4 (0.5 ml), ammonium molybdate (S. Merck), sodium nitrite (Sarabhai Merck) and NTA (Aldrich) were prepared in distilled water.

Beckman 26 and Systronics 118 spectrophotometers were used. A Naina pH-meter for pH measurements was used.

Procedure: In aqueous medium ammonium molybdate (6.0 ml), sodium nitrite (2.0 ml), NTA (1.0 ml) and in varying concentration of DOPA solution (0.2–3.0 ml) were mixed, then pH was adjusted to 7.0 ± 0.1 and the volume made upto 25 ml with distilled water of the same pH. The absorption values were measured at 344 nm after 45 min of mixing the solution and before 230 min. DOPA was estimated from standard Beer's law plot.

Results and Discussion

The optimum conditions for estimation were established after studying the effect of reactants individually on the color saturation and time stability of the complex. The complex formation was completed in 45 min and remained stable up to 230 min at room temperature, and higher temperatures turned the colour to black.

The colour and absorption maximum 344 nm persisted in the pH range of $6.5-7.5 \pm 0.1$, while working pH was 7.0 ± 0.1 .

The concentration ranges when stable colour saturation was obtained are given below.

The concentration ranges for each reagent were arrived at by varying that reagent concentration while keeping all other reagent concentrations constant, i.e. 1.0 ml initially. The optimum concentration of each reagent was maintained for subsequent study (as shown in parenthesis); the concentration ranges of ammonium molybdate, 6.0–8.5 ml (6.0 ml); sodium nitrite, 2.0–8.0 ml (2.0 ml); nitrilotriacetic acid, 1.0–2.2 ml (1.0 ml) were found to be best for full color development.

Beer's law was verified by varying DOPA concentration as described above. In each case, the time-stability or colour saturation or both were affected when reagent concentrations were beyond these ranges. The optimum concentration range for the estimation of DOPA was found to be $1.6-23.6 \mu g ml^{-1}$. Sandell's sensitivity⁸ and relative standard deviation (for six samples at $7.88 \mu g ml^{-1}$ level) were found to be $0.014 \mu g ml^{-1}$ and 0.11% respectively.

The following foreign ions and materials did not show any significant error in determination of $7.8 \mu g$ DOPA in 25 ml in the concentration levels mentioned in parenthesis: Na^+ (50 mg), K^+ (19 mg), Cu^{II} (5 mg), NH_4^+ (3.8 mg), Ca^{II} (650 μg), Mg^{II} (225 μg), Fe^{II} (175 μg), chloride (50 mg), acetate (4 mg);

Determination of DOPA by Spectrophotometric Method

PRADEEP K. SHARMA and K. SRINIVASULU*

School of Studies in Chemistry, Vikram University,
Ujjain-456 010

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THE catecholamines have been determined using various methods¹. Johnson² measured DOPA in their assay by using DOPA decarboxylase preparation to convert dopamine. In the present paper, the brown colour (344 nm) developed due to 3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine (DOPA) with ammonium molybdate, sodium nitrite and nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) in aqueous medium is used for analytical determination after establishing the optimum conditions.

NOTES

oxalate (2 mg), carbonate (400 μ g), bicarbonate (320 μ g), phosphate (275 μ g), sulphate (250 μ g), glucose (14.5 mg), fructose (11.5 mg) and urea (550 μ g).

DOPA in presence of ammonium molybdate, sodium nitrite and NTA alone gave stable colour around 344 nm while other combinations, binary, ternary did not give stable colour. The presence of NTA appeared to stabilise the colour with time.

References

1. F. A. J. MUSKIEF, *J. Labelled Compd.*, 1978, **14**, 497 ; S. R. BINDER and M. E. BIAGGI, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1987, **385**, 941 ; W. R. BLOOR and S. S. BULLEN, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1941, **138**, 727 ; A. LUND, *Actapharmacol.*, 1959, **6**, 127.
2. G. A. JOHNSON, J. M. GREN and R. KUPIECKI, *Clin. Chem.*, 1978, **24**, 1927.
3. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Trace Metals", 3rd. ed., Interscience, New York, 1959, p. 83.